

Study of Clinicohematological Profile of Haemolytic Anaemia in a District Hospital at Rajkot, Gujarat, India**Dhara Satasiya¹, Amit Agravat², Krupal Pujara³, Gauravi Dhruva⁴**¹2nd year Resident, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College & Hospital, Rajkot, India²Professor, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College & Hospital, Rajkot, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College & Hospital, Rajkot, India⁴Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College & Hospital, Rajkot, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Gauravi Dhruva

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Haemolytic anaemia is a group of disorders that cause significant morbidity in children.**Method:** A cross sectional study was conducted at district hospital, Rajkot for a period of 1 year. All cases of newly diagnosed and old cases of haemolytic anaemia on follow up were included. A total of 232 cases from all age group were enrolled. Complete demographic and clinical details of all the patients were noted. Classification of the patients was done based on etiologic profile. Separate recording of the etiologic profile was done for subjects with acute and chronic haemolytic anaemia. Clinical profile of all the subjects was noted.**Results:** While assessing the patients with acute haemolytic anaemia, it was seen that Inherited, Autoimmune, Infections (malaria, dengue, viral hepatitis, enteric fever) and Malignancy, HELLP sx causes were the etiologic profile in 40%, 7%, 12% and 12%, 20% of the patients respectively. While assessing the patients with chronic haemolytic anaemia, it was seen that Inherited (Sickle cell disease/Thalassemia), Blood transfusion complications, Autoimmune conditions, and Bone marrow failure, causes were the etiologic profile in 94%, 0.5%, 1.09% & 1% of the patient respectively. The mean haemoglobin at presentation was 7.39 gm/dl. Massive splenomegaly & hepatomegaly causing discomfort, gall stones were seen in 105 cases. In thalassemia major, 60 cases required frequent transfusions [10-12 per year]. 15 came for less frequent transfusions [6 per year]. Sickle thalassemia & thalassemia intermedia, required one transfusion every 1-2 years. Occasional transfusions were given in sickle cell anaemia also.**Conclusion:** Haemoglobin electrophoresis remains the main investigation of choice in diagnosis of haemolytic anaemia. Thalassemia major is the most severe among other haemolytic anaemia encountered in this series. The study conclude that the need to improve awareness regarding hemoglobinopathies among population also prenatal screening, blood transfusion policies, chelation. policies to prevent complications in transfusion dependent patients.**Keywords:** Clinicohematological profile, Haemolytic Anaemia, Thalassemia.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Anaemia is a decrease in haemoglobin levels from an individual's baseline; however, sex-specific and race-specific reference ranges to make a diagnosis are often used when baseline haemoglobin is not known. Anaemia is often subcategorized into microcytic, normocytic, and macrocytic based on mean corpuscular volume (MCV).

As there are numerous types of anaemia, this laboratory parameter allows clinicians to formulate a practical diagnostic approach. Haemolytic anaemia is classified as normocytic anaemia with an MCV of 80 to 100 fL. It is a form of low haemoglobin due to the destruction of red blood cells, increased haemoglobin catabolism, decreased levels of haemoglobin, and an increase in efforts of

bone marrow to regenerate products Regarding the aetiology, Haemolytic anaemia (HA) can be classified as inherited or acquired and when considering the site of haemolysis, RBCs can be destroyed in the circulation (intravascular) or within macrophages in the spleen or liver (extra vascular). From the clinical perspective, HAs can be acute or chronic and according to the location of the abnormality responsible for the haemolysis, they may be due to intrinsic (intracorpuscular) or extrinsic (extra corpuscular) defects. Hence; the present study was conducted for assessing the clinical-etiological profile of acute and chronic haemolytic anaemia in children and adolescent at tertiary care hospital.

Materials & methods

The present study was conducted for assessment of the clinical & etiological profile of acute and chronic haemolytic anaemia in children and adolescent at tertiary care hospital, Rajkot. A total of 232 patients of all age were included. Complete demographic and clinical details of all the patients were recorded. Classification of the patients was done based on etiologic profile. Separate recording of the etiologic profile was done for subjects with acute and chronic haemolytic anaemia. Clinical profile of all the subjects was also recorded.

Results

Out of 232 patients enrolled, acute haemolytic anaemia was seen in 50 patients while chronic

haemolytic anaemia was seen in the remaining 182 patients.

While assessing the patients with acute haemolytic anaemia, it was seen that Inherited, Autoimmune, Infections (malaria, dengue, viral hepatitis, enteric fever) and Malignancy, HELLP sx causes were the etiologic profile in 40%, 7%, 12% and 12%, 20% of the patients respectively.

While assessing the patients with chronic haemolytic anaemia, it was seen that Inherited (Sickle cell disease/Thalassemia), Blood transfusion complications, Autoimmune conditions, and Bone marrow failure, causes were the etiologic profile in 94%, 0.5%, 1.09% and 1% of the patient respectively.

Table 1: Distribution of subjects according to etiologic profile of acute haemolytic anaemia

Sr. No.	Etiological Profile	Number	Percentage (%)
1	Inherited (G6PD, Acute crisis in sickle)	20	40
2	Autoimmune	3	7
3	Infections (dengue, malaria, viral hepatitis)	6	12
4	HELLP SX	10	20
5	Malignancy	6	12
6	Others (leukemoid reaction, HDN, other ca.)	5	9
7	Total	50	100

Table 2: Distribution of subjects according to etiologic profile of chronic haemolytic anaemia

Sr. No	Etiological Profile	Number	Percentage (%)
1	Autoimmune (SLE)	2	1.09
2	Inherited (Sickle cell disease, Thalassemia)	172	94
3	Bone marrow failure	2	1
4	Blood transfusion complication	1	0.5
5	Others (cardiac valve dx, DIC)	5	2.74
6	Total	182	100

Table 3: Haematological profile of study population

Mean Value	Haemoglobin	Total S.Bilirubin	Retic Count
Beta Thalassemia Major	6.6	47	92
Thalassemia Minor	8.4	1	3
Thalassemia Intermedia	7.4	1	2
Sickle Beta Thalassemia	6.1	1	2
Sickle Cell Dx	7.5	10	30
Sickle Cell Trait	9.9	23	63
Autoimmune	4.9	2	5
Hellp Sx	8	0	10
Infections	11.4	2	6
Malignancy	6.03	1	6
Bone Marrow Failure	6.5	1	2
Bt Complication	4.5	1	1
Others	8.6	7	10
Total	135	97	232

Serum ferritin was done in 65 cases of thalassemia major. Mean serum ferritin was 1421 ng/ml; chelation was started in 36 cases. Icterus was seen in cases. Mean TSB was highest in thalassemia major (3.8mg/dl) followed by sickle cell anaemia,

sickle thalassemia, thalassemia intermedia, thalassemia minor. Mean Hb level of Thalassemia major patient was 6.6 gm/dl. Highest level of reticulocyte count was seen in thalassemia major followed by sickle cell disease.

Table 4: Distribution of haemolytic anaemia according to sociodemographic variable

Type of Haemolytic Anaemia	Sex		Family History			Age Group					
	Female	Male	Total	Yes	No	0-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60
Beta Thalassemia Major	45	47	92	92	0	15	17	55	5	0	0
Thalassemia Minor	2	1	3	0	3	0	1	2	0	0	0
Thalassemia Intermedia	1	1	2	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	0
Sickle Beta Thalassemia	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
Sickle Cell Dx	20	10	30	30	0	2	3	18	4	2	1
Sickle Cell Trait	40	23	63	50	13	3	4	38	6	8	4
Autoimmune	3	2	5	0	5	0	1	3	1	0	0
Hellp Sx	10	0	10	0	10	0	0	6	4	0	0
Infections	4	2	6	0	6	0	1	4	1	0	0
Malignancy	5	1	6	0	6	0	0	2	2	1	1
Bone Marrow Failure	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	1
Bt Complication	0	1	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	0
Others	3	7	10	0	10	1	2	4	2	1	0
Total	135	97	232	174	59	21	31	136	25	12	7

From table 4, it is evident that male to female incidence is 0.9:1 in thalassemia major. Family history is positive in all cases of thalassemia major. History of consanguinity was seen in 70 cases of congenital anaemia. History of similar complaints in siblings was seen in 35 cases. Death of sibling with similar complaints was seen in 3 case of thalassemia major. The maximum numbers of patients were in age group range of 21-30 year.

Graph 1: Distribution of subject according to clinical symptoms

Splenomegaly was seen in all the cases of, Thalassemia major & sickle thalassemia. Spleen >6 cm was seen in 36 cases. Massive splenomegaly causing abdominal discomfort was noted with 6 cases. Splenectomy was undertaken in 5 cases. Jaundice was seen in total 221 cases. Tachycardia was seen in 65 cases.

Table 5: Distribution of cases according to Peripheral smear RBC morphology

Rbc morphology	Hypochromic micro-cytic RBC's	Anisopoikilocytosis	Fragmented RBC's	RBC inclusions
Inherited (G6PD Sickle cell disease, Thalassemia,)	105	135	150	0
Autoimmune	3	4	5	0
Infections (dengue, malaria,	4	4	3	3

viral hepatitis)				
Malignancy & BT complication	5	4	4	0
Others	10	9	9	0

Table no 5 represents distribution of subjects according to RBC series morphology like hypochromic microcytic rbs, anisokilocytosis, fragmented RBC'S & RBC'S inclusion.

Table 7: Distribution of cases according to Peripheral smear WBC morphology

WBC morphology	leukocytosis	Shift to left	Blast like morphology	Leukopenia
Inherited (G6PD Sickle cell disease, Thalassemia,)	85	69	0	41
Autoimmune	2	1	1	1
Infections (dengue, malaria, viral hepatitis)	2	0	0	3
Malignancy & BT complication	5	1	4	0
Others	5	4	0	1

Table no 7 represents distributions of subjects according to peripheral smear wbc series morphology like leukocytosis, leucopenia, shift to left & blast like morphology.

Discussion

Hemoglobinopathies are of worldwide occurrence. Though some geographical areas have high prevalence in India, average frequency of sickle cell gene is around 5%. Highest frequency reported in Orissa 9%, Assam 8.8%, Madhya Pradesh 7.4%, Uttar Pradesh 7.1%. The distribution of beta thalassemia is not uniform in Indian subcontinent. Highest frequency of beta thalassemia trait is reported in Gujarat 10-15%, followed by Sindh 10%, Punjab 6.5%, Tamilnadu and Maharashtra. In our study Out of 232 patients enrolled, acute haemolytic anaemia was seen in 50 patients while chronic haemolytic anaemia was seen in the remaining 182 patients. While assessing the patients with acute haemolytic anaemia, it was seen that Inherited, Autoimmune, Infections (malaria, dengue, viral hepatitis, enteric fever) and Malignancy, HELLP sx causes were the etiologic profile in 40%, 7%, 12% and 12%, 20% of the patients respectively. While assessing the patients with chronic haemolytic anaemia, it was seen that Inherited (Sickle cell disease/Thalassemia), Blood transfusion complications, Autoimmune conditions, and Bone marrow failure, causes were the etiologic profile in 94%, 0.5%, 1.09% and 1% of the patient respectively. The etiologies of hemolysis often are categorized as acquired or hereditary. Common acquired causes of hemolytic anemia are autoimmunity, microangiopathy, and infection. Immune-mediated hemolysis, caused by antierythrocyte antibodies, can be secondary to malignancies, autoimmune disorders, drugs, and transfusion reactions.

Anusha R et al analyzed "The profile of patients with haemolytic anaemia", between 2 months to 12 years of age. In total 41 cases were taken and

conducted over period of 12 months. The study showed beta thalassemia as the most common haemolytic anaemia, followed by malaria, sickle beta thalassemia, thalassemia intermedia, beta thalassemia minor, Sickle cell disease, sickle cell trait, auto immune haemolytic anaemia, and hereditary spherocytosis. The mean haemoglobin at presentation was 7.39 gm/dl. Massive splenomegaly & hepatomegaly causing discomfort, gall stones were seen in 105 cases. In thalassemia major, 60 cases required frequent transfusions [10-12 per year]. 15 came for less frequent transfusions [6 per year]. Sickle thalassemia, thalassemia intermedia, required one transfusion every 1-2 years. Occasional transfusions were given in sickle cell anaemia patient also.

Thalassemia major is the most severe among other haemolytic anaemia encountered in their series. While in our study, on clinically assessing the patients Pale skin, jaundice, dark-Colored urine, fever, weakness, hepatosplenomegaly, tachycardia, were seen in 100%, 95.2%, 92.6%, 53.8%, 77.5%, 45.2%, and 28% of the patients respectively. In Rahul Naithani et al study 80 cases were taken out of which main presenting complaints were pallor (94%), fever (46%), jaundice (51%), bleeding manifestations (10%) and splenomegaly (68%), Jaundice seen in (63%), over time period of 5 months. V P Choudhry et al, study conducted on topic "Clinico-hematological spectrum of auto-immune haemolytic anemia". The common presenting feature was pallor (89%), fever (38%), Jaundice (43%) and hepatomegaly and splenomegaly was seen in 76% and 81% respectively. Haemoglobin level ranged between 1.9 to 11.7 gm/dl (mean 6.8 gm/dl) and reticulocyte counts between 6% to 42% (mean (20.2%). Four patients had thrombocytopenia. Commonest acquired causes of haemolytic anaemia were malaria. The study by Shivashankara et al, hospital based family study, showed that commonest haemolytic anaemia as beta thalassemia (15),

thalassemia trait (20), 2 cases of sickle cell trait, 1 case of sickle cell thalassemia. Preethi et al another hospital based study noted thalassemia major most common -23 cases, followed by sickle cell anaemia- 5 cases, sickle trait 1 case, HS in 4 cases. The male to female incidence was 0.9. Unlike other studies, our study showed more females than males. Male preponderance was seen with chatopadhyay, preethi et al.

Conclusion

Early diagnosis and prompt therapy forms the basis of improved prognosis haemolytic anaemia. Hence; careful recognition of early signs and symptoms is necessary. Though there is lot of useful haematological investigations for the diagnosis of haemolytic anaemia, we conclude that Hb electrophoresis clinches the diagnosis in hemoglobinopathies. Of the prevalent hemoglobinopathies, beta thalassemia major follows a more severe course as compared to other haemolytic anaemia encountered in this series. The impact of genetic diseases, in particular hemoglobinopathies (thalassemia and sickle cell anaemia) on global mortality and morbidity especially in developing countries, world health organization has urged its member states to implement comprehensive national integrated programmes for prevention and management of thalassemia and other hemoglobinopathies. There is scope for improvement and further activities like awareness raising, screening for carriers, premarital screening, antenatal diagnosis, need to be undertaken.

References

1. Kliegman MR, Stanton BF, St gemer WJ, Shor NF. Nelson text book of pediatrics 20th edition: Elsevier publications; 2016.
2. Weather all DJ, Clegg JB: The thalassaemiasyndromes, 4th edition: Oxford Blackwell scientific publications; 2001.
3. Surhone LM, Tennoe MT Henssonow SF, Congenital hemolytic anaemia, Saarbrucken, Germany: VDMV erlog, Dr. Muller; 2010.
4. UNICEF: The state of World's children Oxford: Oxford university press; 1996.
5. Yasish HM- Thalassemia: <http://www.emedicine.com/PED/topic2229.htm>; Accessed 23rd oct 2002.
6. Modell B, Berdoukas V. The clinical approach to Thalassemia: London: Gruns and Stration; 1984.
7. La Nasa G, Caocci G, Argioli F, Giardini C, Locatelli F, Vacca A, Orofino MG, Piras E, Addari MC, Ledda A, Contu L. Unrelated donor stem cell transplantation in adult patients with thalassemia. Bone marrow transplantation. 2005 Dec 1; 36(11):971-5.
8. Verma IC, Choudhry VP, Jain PK. Prevention of thalassemia: a necessity in India. Indian journal of pediatrics. 1992 Nov 1; 59(6):649-54.
9. Manglani M, Lokeshwar MR, Vani VG, Bhatia N, Mhaskar V. 'NESTROFT'--an effective screening test for beta thalassemia trait. Indian pediatrics. 1997Aug; 34(8):702-7.
10. Wild BJ, Bain BJ. Investigations of abnormal-hemoglobins and thalassemia. In: Lews Sin, Bain BJ, Bates I, Dacie and Lewis practical hematology, 9th Balgir RS. The burden of hemoglobinopathies in India and the challenges ahead. Curr sci. 2000 Dec10; 79(11):1536-47.
11. Balgir RS. Spectrum of hemoglobinopathies in the state of Orissa, India: a ten years cohort study. JAPI. 2005 Dec; 53:1021-6.
12. Balgir RS. The genetic burden of hemoglobinopathies with special reference to community health in India and the challenges ahead. Indian J Hematol Blood Transfus. 2002; 20(1):2-7.
13. Varawalla NY, Old JM, Sarkar R, Venkatesan R, Weatherall DJ. The spectrum of β -thalassemia mutations on the Indian subcontinent: the basis for prenatal diagnosis. British journal of haematology. 1991Jun 1; 78(2):242-7.
14. Shivashankara AR, Jaikhani R, Kini A. Hemoglobinopathies in Dharwad, North Karnataka: Ahospital-based study. J Clin Diagnostic Res. 2008; 2:593-9.
15. Preethi BP, Monika K, Maitreyee DS, Rashmi K. A hospital based study of Hereditary Hemolytic Anaemias in Davanagere district of Karnataka, India. Bangladesh journal of medical science. 2010 Jan 1; 9(3):154.